

1. Dataset Description

This trajectory dataset is provided here as an output of ongoing MIT Senseable City Lab research. It is part of the publication “Pedestrian Trajectory Dataset of Public European Squares” by Wolff et al. containing pedestrian trajectories in 39 European squares in pixel- and real-world coordinates.

Attribute	Value
Resolution (pixel)	1280 x 720
Frame rate (fps)	15
Annotated frame rate (fps)	2
Annotated pedestrian number	346,600

2. How to download the data and the code

Data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16362241>

Code: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855754>

3. Disclaimer

The dataset, containing anonymous, georeferenced trajectories of pedestrians on European squares, was made accessible by MIT SCL to the scientific community. The proprietary dataset is not accessible to the public.

4. Dataset creation process

- 1. Data collection:** Places were recorded in the given resolution and compression algorithm of the webcam stream. These varied between HD and 4K.
- 2. Preprocessing of video file:**
 - a. Video length was cut to a length of 30min
 - b. The resolution was set to HD (1280x720 pixels)
 - c. The framerate was set to 15fps
- 3. Object detection algorithm**
 - a. As object detection algorithm a custom trained YOLOv10l_crowdhuman was used.
 - b. The tracking algorithm was Bytetrack.
 - c. Output:
 - i. Annotated video
 - ii. CSV file with trajectories
- 4. Trajectory processing**
 - a. Trajectories with less than 30 frames were removed.
 - b. The center coordinates for each human location (y_{max} = bottom; x_{centre} = x_{max} - x_{min}) were calculated.

- c. Jittering and outliers were removed by applying a sliding window on human coordinates. Window size = 8.
- d. Real-world coordinates were calculated.
 - i. Input files: transformation matrix to transform pixel coordinates into real-world coordinates.
 - ii. Real-world coordinates were saved in the system EPSG: 3857.
- e. Trajectories were masked with the place polygons: Coordinates outside of the place polygon were removed (e.g. when on private ground or road).
- f. Again, all trajectories with less than 30 frames were removed.
- g. The complexity (and size) of trajectories was reduced by reducing the resolution of data points from 15 points per second to two points per second. This increased the processing speed of following calculation steps and removed unneeded complexity. The impact of outliers was reduced by already having calculated the moving average in step 4-c.
- h. A geojson file with all trajectories per place was created. It was used to display trajectories in tools like QGIS or ArcGIS for data validation and visualization.
- i. The walking speed was calculated:
 - i. A column with longitude and latitude was added to avoid distortion of the Mercator projection. long and lat were represented in the crs EPSG:4326.
 - ii. Speed of pedestrians was calculated based on the time column and “real_world_x” and “real_world_y”.
- j. The number of people was calculated for every time of the recording.

5. Content

Place stats:

Item	Usage	Type	Format	Unit	Source
No.	unique identifier for square	Int		number	
City	City name	string		-	
Country	Country name	string		-	
lat	Latitude of square	float		°	
long	Longitude of square	float		°	
Date	Date of recording	string	YYYYMMDD	-	
timeslot	Time-category of recording	String	morning/noon/evening/saturday	-	
rec_dur	Duration of the recording	int		seconds	
people_total	Total number of unique tracker_ids	int			
people_mean	Mean number of tracker_ids per frame	int			

people_median	Median number of tracker_ids per frame	int			
count_staying	total number of people staying (speed <0.2m/s for more than 5s)	int			
count_walking	total number of people walking (people not staying)	int			
speed_total_mean	Mean speed of all people	float			
speed_total_median	Median speed of all people	float			
speed_total_std	std speed of all people	float			
speed_walking_mean	Mean speed of people classified as walking	float			
speed_walking_median	Median speed of people classified as walking	float			
speed_walking_std	std speed of people classified as walking	float			
speed_staying_mean	Mean speed of people classified as staying	float			
speed_staying_median	Median speed of people classified as staying	float			
speed_staying_std	std speed of people classified as staying	float			
dur_sum	Total accumulated time of people detected on square	float			
dur_mean	Mean time per tracker_id detected on square	float			
dur_median	Median time per tracker_id detected on square	float			
dur_std	std time per tracker_id detected on square	float			

Residents	Number of residents in city	int			Wikipedia
café	Presence of cafe	string	Yes/No		Google earth
fountain	Presence of fountain	string	Yes/No		Google earth
area	area of square	int		m2	our data collection
Temp	city temperature during recording	Int		°C	API
Windspeed	city windspeed during recording	Int		km/h	API
precipitation	city precipitation during recording	Int		mm	API
humidity	city humidity during recording	Int	0...100	%	API
description	description for weather during recording	string	partly cloudy/sunny/Mist	-	API
Rec_time	exact time of recording	time	hh:mm:ss	-	
description	weather description	string	sunny/partly cloudy/clear/patchy rain nearby/mist		API

Trajectory files:

Item	Usage	Type	Format	Unit	Source
x_min	the left edge of the bounding box in pixel coordinates	float			YOLOv10
x_max	the right edge of the bounding box in pixel coordinates	float			YOLOv10
y_min	the top edge of the bounding box in pixel coordinates	float			YOLOv10
y_max	the bottom edge of the bounding box in pixel coordinates	float			YOLOv10
centre_x	$(x_{max} + x_{min})/2$	float			
centre_y	y_{max}	float			
centre_x_sw	sliding window over centre_x (window_size = 8)	float			
centre_y_sw	sliding window over centre_y (window_size = 8)	float			
real_world_x	centre_x georeferenced	float		ESPG:3857	
real_world_y	centre_y georeferenced	float		ESPG:3857	
real_world_sw_x	sliding window over real_world_x (window_size = 8)	float			

real_world_sw_y	sliding window over real_world_y (window_size = 8)	Float			
longitude	real_world_sw_x transformed	Float		ESPG:4326	
latitude	real_world_sw_x transformed	Float		ESPG:4326	
class_id	The ID of a class follows the definitions of the COCO dataset.	Float		In this research always '0' for the class human	YOLOv10
confidence	percentage of confidence that the bounding box describes the specific class	Float	0...1		YOLOv10
tracker_id	a unique ID for every detected human	Int			Bytetrack
frame_index	The video frame on which the detection was performed. For a video with 15 frames per second (fps), there is a time difference of 0.067 seconds between every frame.	Float			
speed	Calculated based on longitude and latitude	Float		m/s	
nr_people	number of unique tracker_ids calculated for each frame	Int			

Location of places:

6. Sample Data

x_min	y_min	x_max	y_max	class_id	confidence	tracker_id	class_name	frame_index	center_x	center_y	time	sliding_window_x	sliding_window_y	real_world_x	
746.3938	513.26587	765.6887	562.2053	0	0.8125615		1 person	3	756.0412	537.7356	0	756.0412		537.7356	1404318.461503047
746.4742	513.32166	765.87726	562.1826	0	0.80789226		1 person	4	756.1757	537.7521	0.5	756.1084		537.7439	1404318.4634095458
746.804	513.43726	766.23376	561.32043	0	0.7893736		1 person	12	756.5189	537.3788	1	756.5295		537.7246	1404318.392720347
746.8198	513.3198	765.7392	561.00336	0	0.79280907		1 person	19	756.2795	537.1616	1.5	756.3296		537.4154	1404318.355665903
746.7589	514.0412	763.2038	561.41345	0	0.7915186		1 person	27	754.9814	537.7273	2	755.7485		537.3374	1404318.355239134
746.11084	513.8496	764.5547	559.7447	0	0.5106642		1 person	34	755.3328	536.7972	2.5	754.9628		536.9816	1404318.208106223
745.51953	514.30286	763.70593	553.98315	0	0.43309104		1 person	42	754.6127	534.143	3	755.1227		535.0323	1404317.6327043844
745.69885	513.80505	765.2197	557.6544	0	0.44359618		1 person	49	755.4593	535.7297	3.5	754.8634		535.5183	1404318.012804484
745.9084	514.053	764.3966	561.1278	0	0.3352502		1 person	62	755.1525	537.5904	4	755.1068		536.4396	1404318.3334665801
745.49677	514.04675	764.7652	562.5146	0	0.40925398		1 person	64	755.131	538.2807	4.5	755.1418		536.5709	1404318.4632019536
746.34485	514.19666	764.8515	549.5224	0	0.26386505		1 person	72	755.5982	531.8595	5	755.4322		533.5716	1404317.2250336106
745.95197	513.36786	768.13776	560.2543	0	0.5466937		1 person	79	757.0449	536.8111	5.5	757.0147		536.7813	1404318.3080216807
746.28864	513.8275	767.74194	559.36053	0	0.45812282		1 person	87	757.0153	536.594	6	757.0008		536.7545	1404318.2225074477
746.1903	513.63196	767.713	559.13763	0	0.43639454		1 person	94	756.9516	536.3848	6.5	757.0267		536.5417	1404318.1994261432
746.0427	512.92096	768.49335	558.6809	0	0.4145014		1 person	102	757.268	535.8009	7	757.1089		536.1179	1404318.165593366
746.0886	513.35333	767.50684	557.79456	0	0.4743349		1 person	109	756.7977	535.5739	7.5	757.1518		535.6937	1404318.066849096
746.12994	513.23895	767.44403	556.55646	0	0.45943314		1 person	117	756.787	534.8977	8	756.837		535.1635	1404317.9479392057